

Perception of Orthodontic Treatment in Individuals with different age groups

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Abstract

Aim: This study aimed to evaluate the perception of orthodontic treatment among individuals across different age groups, assessing factors such as age, gender, geographical location, educational background, and socioeconomic status that influence treatment-seeking behaviour. **Methods:** A questionnaire-based study was conducted with 100 participants divided into four age groups (5–10, 11–20, 21–30, and 31–40 years). Data were collected on demographics, perceptions of orthodontic treatment, and barriers to care. Statistical analysis was performed using the chi-square test and descriptive statistics. **Results:** The majority of participants (49%) were aged 21–30 years, with no representation from the 5–10 years group. Females (55%) showed slightly higher participation than males (45%). Urban residents (53%) marginally outnumbered rural participants (47%). Most respondents were graduates (41%), and 76% belonged to the middle-income group (annual income: 1–5 lakhs). Key findings included high aesthetic concerns (92.5% desired dental improvement), strong motivation for braces (62.7%), and perceived benefits in oral health (91%), self-confidence (100%), and social interactions (98.5%). Financial constraints (86.6%) and appearance-related worries (86.6%) were major barriers. **Conclusion:** Younger individuals, particularly females and those with higher education, were more likely to seek orthodontic treatment. Urban residence and middle-income status also influenced participation. Addressing financial barriers and enhancing awareness in rural and lower-income populations could improve access to orthodontic care.

Keywords: Orthodontic treatment perception, age groups, dental aesthetics, socioeconomic factors, barriers to orthodontic care, questionnaire study

Introduction

The commencement of orthodontic treatment is influenced not only by the severity of malocclusion but also by background factors such as age, sex, area of living, socioeconomic status, and educational background, which shape perceptions toward treatment and must be evaluated alongside clinical parameters through qualitative approaches.¹ Many individuals pursue orthodontic care primarily for esthetic improvements rather than to address functional impairments, with studies showing that both patients and parents often place higher value on enhanced dental appearance over oral function.² Dental attractiveness significantly impacts the decision to seek orthodontic treatment, with perceptions varying widely across individuals, cultures, and socioeconomic groups, where an acceptable dental appearance for one person may not be for another.³ Frequency of orthodontic visits is also affected by psychological factors such as self-esteem and social confidence, while financial constraints in lower socioeconomic groups and differences in educational background limit access to care.^{4,5} Moreover, the elective nature of orthodontic treatment highlights the importance of patient autonomy, necessitating active participation of both patients and parents in treatment decisions, and understanding motivational factors can foster a positive attitude towards orthodontic care.⁶

Subjects and Methods

Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Review Board prior to the commencement of the study. As this was a questionnaire-based study with no invasive procedures performed on humans or animals, no separate ethical approval for clinical intervention was required. The study was conducted in the Department of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopaedics, Faculty of Dental Science, Nadiad, Gujarat. A total of 100 participants were included in the study, divided into four age groups: 5–10 years, 11–20 years, 21–30 years, and 31–40 years.

The **inclusion criteria** consisted of individuals seeking orthodontic treatment who belonged to one of the specified age groups. **Exclusion criteria** consisted of Participants who had previously undergone orthodontic treatment, individuals below 5 years or above 40 years of age, and those with systemic diseases or other disabilities.

Data were collected using a specially designed offline questionnaire. Participants and, where necessary, their parents provided informed consent (Annexure I) after a detailed explanation of the study objectives. Consent was considered implied through the participants' willingness to complete the questionnaire. Participation was entirely voluntary, and individuals could withdraw from the study at any time without any obligation toward the study team. No identifying information was collected to ensure anonymity, and confidentiality of the collected data was strictly maintained. No interventional procedures were applied, and no incentives or rewards were offered for participation.

Participants perceptions regarding orthodontic treatment were assessed based on their responses. Demographic information including age, sex, area of living, socioeconomic status, and educational background of both the participants and their parents was collected prior to filling out the questionnaire. The collected data aimed to assess the overall frequencies of positive and negative perceptions toward orthodontic treatment, and to identify barriers or negative perceptions preventing individuals from receiving orthodontic care.

Statistical Analysis

Data analysis was performed using the chi-square test to identify associations between categorical variables. Descriptive statistics, including numbers and percentages, were used to summarize results for categorical measurements.

Results

The survey reveals a significant concern among respondents (55.2%) regarding the appearance of their teeth, with a striking 92.5% expressing a desire to change their dental aesthetics. The acknowledgment of the need for straightening teeth is widespread, as indicated by the same percentage. Motivation for orthodontic treatment, particularly with braces, is notable at 62.7%, despite concerns about the potential emotional and social impact. Respondents overwhelmingly believe in the benefits of orthodontic intervention, expecting improvements in oral health (91%), self-confidence (100%), and social interactions (98.5%). Emotional and social factors play a substantial role, with worries about treatment (77.6%) and appearance with braces (86.6%) being prominent. Financial considerations also weigh in, as 86.6% perceive orthodontic treatment as expensive, emphasizing the importance of cost-effective options and transparent communication. Despite concerns, a large majority (85.1%) express a general interest in orthodontic treatment, indicating a willingness to explore interventions for enhanced dental aesthetics.

Figure 1: Age

The majority of the participants (49%) belonged to the 21–30 years age group, followed closely by the 11–20 years age group, which constituted 45% of the total sample. A smaller proportion, 6%, was from the 31–40 years age group. Notably, there were no participants recorded from the 5–10 years group, despite it being one of the predefined categories in the study's inclusion criteria. This suggests that most individuals seeking orthodontic treatment in this study were young adults, with minimal representation from older adults and no representation from young children.

Figure 2: Gender

Out of the total sample, 55% were female (82 participants), while 45% were male (68 participants). This indicates a slightly higher participation of females compared to males, suggesting that females may have a greater interest or motivation towards seeking orthodontic treatment in the studied group.

Figure 3: Area of living

53% of participants (79 individuals) were from urban areas, while 47% (71 individuals) were from rural areas. This slight urban predominance suggests that individuals from urban settings were marginally more likely to seek orthodontic treatment compared to those from rural backgrounds.

Figure 4: Education

The majority were graduates (41 participants), followed closely by those who had completed higher secondary school (32 participants) and primary school (31 participants). Fewer participants had education up to college level (27 participants) and secondary school level (19 participants). Very minimal participation from individuals with lower education levels was observed, with no significant representation beyond the blue bars shown. This indicates that individuals with higher educational attainment were more likely to seek or have awareness towards orthodontic treatment.

Figure 5: Annual income

A large majority, 76% (114 participants), had an annual income between 1 to 5 lakhs. About 21% (31 participants) reported an income of more than 5 lakhs annually, while only 3% of participants had an annual income between 25,000 to 1 lakh. This indicates that most participants belonged to a middle-income group, with fewer individuals from lower-income or higher-income backgrounds.

Discussion

The demographic characteristics of participants in this study show a notable trend towards younger individuals seeking orthodontic treatment, particularly those aged between 21 to 30 years (49%), followed closely by the 11 to 20 years age group (45%). This finding aligns with the growing body of research indicating that orthodontic treatment is most sought after in adolescence and early adulthood when individuals are more conscious of their appearance and oral health.⁷ Several studies have highlighted that younger patients tend to be more motivated for orthodontic treatment due to concerns about aesthetics, which is consistent with the present study's findings regarding the age distribution.⁸ The absence of participants from the 5–10 years age group could reflect a tendency to prioritize orthodontic interventions during later childhood or adolescence, when the permanent dentition is fully established and treatment outcomes are more predictable.⁹

Gender distribution in the current study, with a slightly higher proportion of females (55%) compared to males (45%), reflects similar trends in previous research where females have been found to be more likely to seek orthodontic treatment than males.¹⁰ This gender difference may be attributed to greater societal emphasis on female aesthetics and a more proactive approach to oral care. Furthermore, a study by Harrison et al. suggested that females may also experience higher rates of self-consciousness about dental appearance, motivating them to seek corrective treatments.¹¹

The finding that 53% of participants came from urban areas and 47% from rural areas indicates a relatively equal distribution of individuals seeking orthodontic care based on geographical location. However, it is important to note that previous studies have often found a stronger inclination towards orthodontic treatment among urban populations due to better access to healthcare facilities, higher income levels, and increased awareness.¹² The present study's relatively balanced urban-rural distribution may suggest that the accessibility of orthodontic care is gradually improving in rural areas, potentially due to greater availability of dental professionals and growing awareness through media.

Educational background played a significant role in the decision to seek orthodontic treatment, with 41% of participants being graduates. This finding is consistent with previous studies that have shown that individuals with higher educational attainment are more likely to be aware of, and seek, orthodontic care due to increased health literacy and better understanding of the benefits of orthodontic treatment.¹³ A study by Mazhari et al. emphasized that higher education levels correlate with improved oral health awareness and a greater likelihood of seeking dental treatment.¹⁴

In terms of socioeconomic status, a majority of participants (76%) reported an annual income between 1 to 5 lakhs, indicating that the middle-income group is the most likely to pursue orthodontic treatment. This is consistent with findings from various studies that suggest orthodontic care is often more accessible to individuals within the middle-income bracket, as they have both the financial means and the awareness necessary to seek treatment.¹⁵ A smaller proportion of participants (21%) earned more than 5 lakhs, while only 3% earned less than 1 lakh, highlighting the challenges faced by lower-income individuals in accessing orthodontic care, despite growing awareness of its benefits.

Conclusion

This study highlights key demographic factors influencing the demand for orthodontic treatment, with a clear tendency for younger individuals, particularly those in the 21–30 years age group, to seek care. The slight female predominance in the sample aligns with previous findings suggesting greater aesthetic concerns among females. The urban-rural distribution also reflects a marginally higher inclination for treatment among urban residents, potentially due to better access to healthcare facilities. Educational attainment emerged as a significant factor, with higher education levels correlating with increased awareness and willingness to pursue orthodontic care. Additionally, the socioeconomic status of participants indicated that most individuals from the middle-income group were seeking treatment, while those from lower- or higher-income brackets were less represented. These findings emphasize the need for targeted interventions to improve awareness and access to orthodontic care, especially among rural and lower-income populations.

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